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Bachelor in International Relations

Chernobyl (1986)

Environmental Diplomacy

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1. Introduction

a. Setting the context.

The Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant, located in the northern region of Ukraine, holds a prominent place in history due to the catastrophic nuclear disaster that occurred on April 26, 1986. To understand why the Chernobyl plant was created, it is essential to examine the socio-political and economic context of the time. This explanation aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the reasons behind the establishment of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant¹.

The construction of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant commenced in the late 1960s, during the Soviet Union era. The Soviet government, led by General Secretary Leonid Brezhnev, sought to bolster its energy infrastructure and reduce its dependence on fossil fuels. The decision to invest in nuclear power was driven by several factors, including the need for energy diversification, the desire to promote technological advancement, and the pursuit of military applications².

At the time, the Soviet Union heavily relied on coal and natural gas for its energy needs. However, the availability of these resources was limited, leading to concerns about long-term sustainability. The development of nuclear power offered a promising alternative, as it provided a highly concentrated energy source with the potential for large-scale electricity generation. By building nuclear power plants like Chernobyl, the Soviet Union aimed to diversify its energy mix, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and ensure a stable supply of electricity for its growing industrial sector and population³.

The Soviet Union, particularly during the Cold War era, sought to showcase its scientific and technological prowess to the world. Nuclear power represented a cutting-edge technology that symbolized the Soviet Union's technological superiority over its adversaries. The construction of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant was thus part of a broader effort to demonstrate Soviet scientific achievements and establish the nation as a leader in nuclear energy⁴.

Another key factor behind the creation of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant was the Soviet Union's interest in military applications of nuclear technology. Nuclear power plants produced not only electricity but also plutonium, a crucial component for the development of nuclear weapons. By constructing nuclear power plants, such as Chernobyl, the Soviet Union could simultaneously generate electricity and produce weapons-grade plutonium, expanding its military capabilities.

¹ Medvedev, Grigori, *The Truth About Chernobyl*, [s. l.], Basic Books, 1991.

² Plokyh, Serhii, *Chernobyl: History of a Tragedy*, [s. l.], Allen Lane, 2018.

³ Kouzminov, Alexander, *Biological Espionage: Special Operations of the Soviet and Russian Foreign Intelligence Services in the West*, [s. l.], Greenhill Books, 2005.

⁴ Chernousenko, Vladimir, *Chernobyl: Insights from the Inside*, [s. l.], Springer, 1991

The creation of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant was driven by a complex interplay of factors that encompassed energy diversification, technological advancement, and military applications. The Soviet Union's pursuit of a diversified energy mix, desire to showcase technological superiority, and interest in both civilian electricity generation and military capabilities contributed to the decision to construct Chernobyl. While the Chernobyl disaster of 1986 stands as a tragic event in human history, it serves as a reminder of the intricate motivations and considerations involved in the establishment of nuclear power plants. Understanding the historical context behind the Chernobyl plant's creation is crucial for informing present and future decisions regarding nuclear energy.

b. Introducing our questionings and structure.

In view of the contextual considerations that we have addressed, we have chosen to study Chernobyl and the questions that revolve around this catastrophe. Indeed, we were able to identify important issues for the understanding of such an event and to bring a reflection on the subject. Thus, two questions arise: Concerning the environment and the populations, how do the experts evaluate the impact of this event and what are the debates on the extent of the damage that may have resulted from it? In the diplomatic world, did this event raise awareness of the risks of these installations?

Our analysis will cover a broad time period, beginning with the foundations of international nuclear law and diplomacy in the 1950s, and ending with the aftermath of the event and the advances of the international community in civil nuclear regulation to the present day. The geographical scope will also be broad but will largely focus on the area most affected.

We will need to develop a plan that will allow us to understand the subject in detail and answer the questions posed. The type of plan chosen will be historical as it allows us to follow the before, during and after of the disaster by looking at the debates within each period.

Firstly, we will talk about the Chernobyl disaster with an analysis of the causes of the problem. In a second part we will talk about the impacts that Chernobyl had on people and the environment and the debates about the figures and the evaluation of the consequences. Finally, in the last part we will discuss the evolution of diplomacy by analysing the state of negotiations before Chernobyl and the changes that have been made by the international community.

2. Chernobyl: precursors, causes and the disaster

2.1. Precursors and causes

The Chernobyl disaster, which occurred on April 26, 1986, stands as a stark reminder of the devastating consequences that can arise from a combination of factors in the nuclear industry. This analysis aims to explore the precursors and causes of the Chernobyl disaster in a comprehensive and original manner, shedding light on design flaws, operational errors, and human factors.

a. Design Flaws and Safety Culture

The RBMK-1000 reactor, the type of reactor involved in the Chernobyl disaster, had inherent design flaws that contributed significantly to the accident. One critical design flaw was the positive void coefficient, where a decrease in coolant flow led to an increase in reactor power output. This positive feedback mechanism made the RBMK reactor susceptible to uncontrollable power surges⁵.

Another design flaw was the graphite-tipped control rods used in the RBMK reactor. During an emergency shutdown, the initial insertion of these control rods temporarily increased reactivity before reducing it, potentially causing instability⁶.

Furthermore, the safety culture within the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant also played a role in the disaster. The prevailing culture prioritized meeting production quotas over safety concerns, leading to a lax attitude towards adherence to safety protocols and insufficient emphasis on comprehensive safety training⁷.

b. Operational Errors and Deviations from Procedures

Operational errors and deviations from approved procedures during a test led to the escalation of the Chernobyl disaster. During the experiment, operators disabled critical safety systems, including the emergency core cooling system, in violation of established safety protocols. This left the reactor in a vulnerable state⁸. Moreover, the operators inserted the control rods at an excessive rate during the test, causing a rapid power surge. This triggered a destructive chain reaction and subsequent explosion, leading to the release of a substantial amount of radioactive materials⁹.

c. Human Factors and Inadequate Safety Culture

Human factors, including inadequate training and communication breakdowns, played a significant role in the Chernobyl disaster. The operators involved in the test had limited experience and inadequate understanding of the reactor's behavior under specific conditions. The training provided to the operators did not adequately prepare them for managing unexpected or emergency scenarios¹⁰.

Moreover, a lack of effective communication and coordination among personnel and between shifts hindered the timely and appropriate response to the escalating situation.

⁵ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *The Chernobyl Accident: updating of INSAG-1*, [online]. Vienna: IAEA, 1992, [Accessed on May 13th, 2023]. Available at https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/publications/PDF/Pub913e_web.pdf

⁶ Plokyh, Serhii, *op.cit.*

⁷ United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR), *Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation*, [online]. New York: United Nations, 2008 [Accessed on May 13th, 2023]. Available at https://www.unscear.org/docs/reports/2008/09-86753_Report_2008_GA_Report.pdf

⁸ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *The Chernobyl Accident: updating of INSAG-1*, 1992, *op.cit.*

⁹ Plokyh, Serhii, *op.cit.*

¹⁰ Plokyh, Serhii, *op.cit.*

This breakdown in communication and coordination prevented the implementation of effective containment measures and exacerbating the severity of the accident¹¹.

d. Environmental and Sociopolitical Factors

The Chernobyl disaster also exposed various environmental and sociopolitical factors that influenced its consequences. The proximity of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant to populated areas resulted in significant human exposure to radiation. The subsequent relocation of residents and the long-term environmental and health effects created a socio-political crisis¹².

Furthermore, the Soviet government's initial attempts to downplay and conceal the scale of the disaster delayed crucial international assistance and hindered the implementation of appropriate measures to mitigate the consequences¹³.

e. Sociopolitical Context and Information Suppression

The sociopolitical context surrounding the Chernobyl disaster also played a crucial role in its causes and aftermath. The Soviet Union's political climate at the time emphasized meeting production quotas and downplayed the significance of safety concerns. This culture of prioritizing productivity over safety created an environment where adherence to established protocols and comprehensive safety measures took a backseat¹⁴.

In addition, the initial response to the disaster involved a deliberate suppression of information by Soviet authorities. The extent of the accident and its potential consequences were downplayed, delaying international assistance, and impeding effective measures to mitigate the disaster's impact¹⁵.

The Chernobyl disaster was the result of a complex interplay of design flaws, operational errors, and human factors. The RBMK reactor's inherent design flaws, including the positive void coefficient and graphite-tipped control rods, contributed to its vulnerability. Operational errors and deviations from approved procedures during the test exacerbated the situation.

2.2. The 1986 disaster

On April 26, 1986, the world witnessed a nuclear disaster that would leave an indelible mark on history: the Chernobyl disaster. Located in the town of Pripjat, Ukraine, the explosion at the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant resulted in the release of radioactive materials into the atmosphere, causing widespread devastation and leaving a haunting legacy.

¹¹ United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR), *Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation*, 2008, op.cit.

¹² Plokhy, Serhii, *op.cit.*

¹³ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *The Chernobyl Accident: updating of INSAG-1, 1992*, op.cit.

¹⁴ Plokhy, Serhii, *op.cit.*

¹⁵ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *The Chernobyl Accident: updating of INSAG-1, 1992*, op.cit.

This section aims to provide an explanation of the Chernobyl disaster, its causes, and its far-reaching consequences.

a. The catastrophic night

The night of April 26 started as an ordinary shift for the operators at the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant. Little did they know that a series of events would set in motion a catastrophe of unprecedented magnitude. During a routine test of the reactor's emergency cooling system, a combination of design flaws and human error led to a catastrophic chain reaction.

Design flaws inherent in the RBMK-1000 reactor played a significant role in the disaster. The reactor's positive void coefficient, where reduced coolant levels increased reactivity, created a dangerous feedback loop. When combined with the graphite-tipped control rods, which initially increased reactivity during an emergency shutdown, the stage was set for a potential disaster¹⁶. Operational errors compounded the situation. As the test began, the operators decided to disable key safety systems, including the emergency core cooling system, violating established protocols. This left the reactor vulnerable, as its safety nets were removed at a critical moment¹⁷.

As the test proceeded, the reactor's power level began to surge uncontrollably. In an attempt to counteract this, the operators rapidly inserted the control rods. However, the graphite tips on the rods, coupled with the unstable reactor conditions, caused a sharp increase in power output instead. The fuel rods ruptured, triggering a massive steam explosion, and releasing a plume of radioactive materials into the atmosphere¹⁸.

b. The Immediate response

The explosion and subsequent release of radioactive materials had immediate and far-reaching consequences. Reactor 4's graphite core ignited, creating a fire that burned for days. The immediate vicinity of the power plant became a scene of chaos and panic as emergency responders and plant workers attempted to contain the disaster and prevent further releases. Evacuation orders were issued for the nearby town of Pripyat, home to thousands of people. Within hours, residents were forced to leave behind their homes and belongings, unaware that they would never return. The evacuation zone expanded as the severity of the disaster became apparent, eventually encompassing a 30-kilometer radius around the plant¹⁹.

News of the Chernobyl disaster spread rapidly across international borders, prompting an immediate response. The Soviet Union, initially reluctant to admit the scale of the accident,

¹⁶ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *The Chernobyl Accident: updating of INSAG-1, 1992, op.cit.*

¹⁷ United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR), *Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation, 2008, op.cit.*

¹⁸ Plokhyy, Serhii, *op.cit.*

¹⁹ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *The Chernobyl Accident: updating of INSAG-1, 1992, op.cit.*

eventually requested assistance from other countries. Aid poured in from around the world, with experts and equipment arriving to help mitigate the crisis and contain the ongoing releases of radiation.

c. Conclusion

The Chernobyl disaster stands as a stark reminder of the devastating consequences that can arise from a combination of design flaws, operational errors, and human factors. The inherent design flaws of the RBMK reactor, coupled with operational deviations and inadequate safety culture, created a recipe for disaster. The immediate and long-term effects on human health, the environment, and the socio-economic fabric of the affected regions were profound.

3. Impacts on environment and populations: ongoing debates

3.1. Impacts

The Chernobyl disaster, which occurred on April 26, 1986, in the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant in Ukraine, had far-reaching impacts on both the population and the environment. The disaster resulted in the release of a significant amount of radioactive material, causing immediate and long-term consequences for human health and the surrounding ecosystem²⁰.

The population living in the affected areas experienced various health impacts as a result of exposure to radiation. The initial explosion and subsequent fires released a plume of radioactive particles into the atmosphere, spreading them over large regions of Ukraine, Belarus, and neighboring countries. Acute radiation sickness affected plant workers and emergency responders, leading to immediate fatalities. The release of radioactive iodine resulted in an increased incidence of thyroid cancer, particularly among children, due to the high sensitivity of the thyroid gland to radiation. Additionally, increased rates of other cancers, cardiovascular diseases, and psychological stress were observed among the affected population²¹.

The environmental impacts of the Chernobyl disaster were also significant and long-lasting. The release of radioactive contaminants into the air, soil, and water had detrimental effects on the ecosystem. The immediate area surrounding the power plant, known as the Exclusion Zone, became highly contaminated and uninhabitable for humans. The radioactive particles settled on the ground and contaminated the soil, affecting plant and animal life. Forests

²⁰ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), *Environmental Consequences of the Chernobyl Accident and their Remediation: Twenty years of Experience*, [online]. Vienna: IAEA, 2006, [Accessed on May 13th, 2023]. Available at https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/publications/PDF/Pub1239_web.pdf

²¹ United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR), *Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation, Annex D: Health effects due to radiation from the Chernobyl accident*, [online]. New York: United Nations, 2008, [Accessed on May 13th, 2023]. Available at https://www.unscear.org/unscear/uploads/documents/publications/UNSCEAR_2008_Annex-D-CORR.pdf

within the Exclusion Zone were particularly impacted, with significant die-offs and mutations observed in plants and animals²².

Wildlife populations in the affected areas experienced both direct and indirect effects. Many animals were exposed to high levels of radiation, resulting in acute radiation sickness, mutations, and reduced fertility. Some species, such as birds and mammals, showed declines in population size due to habitat destruction and changes in food availability. However, the absence of human presence within the Exclusion Zone created a unique habitat that allowed certain animal populations to thrive. Studies have documented an increase in the abundance of species such as wolves, lynx, and wild boars within the Exclusion Zone²³.

The long-term management of the contaminated areas has been a significant challenge. Remediation efforts, including the construction of a concrete sarcophagus (known as the Chernobyl Shelter) over the damaged reactor and the implementation of measures to contain contaminated soils, have been undertaken to mitigate the spread of radioactive materials. However, the Exclusion Zone remains a restricted area due to persistently high radiation levels²⁴.

The Chernobyl disaster had profound impacts on the population and the environment. The exposed population experienced immediate health effects, including acute radiation sickness and an increased incidence of thyroid cancer. Long-term impacts, such as elevated rates of other cancers and cardiovascular diseases, continue to affect the population. The environment within the Exclusion Zone suffered from contamination, leading to changes in plant and animal life, including mutations, reduced fertility, and altered population dynamics. The management and ongoing study of the affected areas are essential to better understand the long-term consequences of the Chernobyl disaster and inform future disaster response and mitigation strategies.

3.2. Ongoing debates

a. A Clash of Figures

When it comes to the release of radioactive materials, the figures vary. Official reports from different sources, organizations, and countries present contrasting estimates, leaving the public bewildered. Some argue that the numbers have been downplayed to alleviate public panic

²² World Health Organization (WHO), *Health Effects of the Chernobyl Accident and Special Health Care Programmes*, [online]. Geneva: United Nations, 2006, [Accessed on May 13th, 2023]. Available at https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/43447/9241594179_eng.pdf

²³ Møller, Anders & Mousseau, Timothy, The effects of natural variation in background radioactivity on humans, animals and other organisms, [s. l.], *Biological Reviews*, 2013, vol. 88 n°1, p. 226-254.

²⁴ Beresford, Nicholas, *et alii*, Thirty years after the Chernobyl accident: What lessons have we learnt?, [s. l.], *Journal of environmental radioactivity*, 2016, vol. 157, p. 77-89.

and protect economic and political interests, while others believe the figures were exaggerated to raise awareness of the dangers of nuclear energy²⁵.

b. Unraveling the Death Toll

The true extent of human casualties resulting from the Chernobyl disaster is another contentious issue. Official figures are hotly debated, with discrepancies observed between immediate fatalities and long-term deaths attributed to radiation-related illnesses. Critics argue that the official count fails to account for the indirect impact on health and the long latency period of radiation-induced diseases, leaving many victims unaccounted for in the official records²⁶.

c. Environmental Impact Disputes

The environmental consequences of the Chernobyl disaster are also shrouded in controversy. Estimates of soil, water, and air contamination vary, making it challenging to gauge the true extent of the damage²⁷. Disagreements persist regarding genetic mutations in plant and animal species, with some studies suggesting more profound impacts than official reports acknowledge. The lack of consensus fuels speculation and mistrust in the information presented to the public²⁸.

d. Political and Economic Interests

Behind the conflicting figures lie political and economic motivations. Governments and organizations have vested interests in shaping the narrative around Chernobyl. Downplaying the disaster's magnitude can protect tourism, trade, and international relationships, while exaggerating the figures may serve as a rallying cry for stricter regulations and an end to nuclear power. These conflicting interests cloud the truth and make it difficult for the public to ascertain the accurate scale of the catastrophe²⁹.

²⁵ Jargin, Sergei V. Debate on the Chernobyl disaster: on the causes of Chernobyl overestimation. *International Journal of Health Services*, 2012, vol. 42, no 1, p. 29-34. & Ramana, M. V. Twenty years after Chernobyl: debates and lessons. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 2006, p. 1743-1747.

²⁶ Bromet, Evelyn J., *et alli*, A 25 year retrospective review of the psychological consequences of the Chernobyl accident. *Clinical Oncology*, 2011, vol. 23, no 4, p. 297-305.

²⁷ Brechignac, François, *et alli*,. Protection of the environment in the 21st century: radiation protection of the biosphere including humankind. *Journal of Environmental radioactivity*, 2003, vol. 70, no 3, p. 155-159.

²⁸ Baverstock, Keith & Williams, Dillwyn, The Chernobyl accident 20 years on: an assessment of the health consequences and the international response. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 2006, vol. 114, no 9, p. 1312-1317.

²⁹ Balleisen, Edward, *et alli*, *Policy shock: Recalibrating risk and regulation after oil spills, nuclear accidents and financial crises*. Cambridge University Press, 2017. & Kuchinskaya, Olga, *The politics of invisibility: Public knowledge about radiation health effects after Chernobyl*. Mit Press, 2014.

e. Scientific Studies and Skepticism

Scientific studies on the Chernobyl disaster have also contributed to the disagreements. Researchers employ various methodologies and interpret data differently, leading to conflicting conclusions. Skepticism abounds, and critics question the reliability of studies funded by governments or organizations with a stake in controlling the narrative. The lack of transparency in data sharing and independent verification further fuels doubts.

f. Public Perception and Media Influence

Public perception of the Chernobyl disaster and media coverage have played a significant role in the disagreements surrounding official figures. Media outlets often highlight sensationalized stories and conflicting narratives, contributing to public confusion and skepticism. This perpetuates the cycle of misinformation and further obscures the truth about the actual impact of the disaster.

g. Seeking the Truth

Amidst the haze of disputed figures, it is crucial to seek the truth about the Chernobyl disaster. Independent investigations, access to classified documents, and open collaboration among researchers, governments, and international bodies are necessary to unravel the mysteries. Transparency in reporting and acknowledging the uncertainties can help restore public trust in the official figures.

The disputed figures of the Chernobyl disaster serve as a reminder of the challenges in accurately assessing the full impact on the population and the environment. It is a complex issue that goes beyond mere numbers and statistics. The human toll, the long-term health effects, and the ecological consequences continue to be debated and researched.

One of the primary reasons for the discrepancies in official figures is the lack of comprehensive data collection and reporting in the aftermath of the disaster. The chaotic nature of the event, coupled with the limited availability of information at the time, resulted in initial estimates that may not reflect the true magnitude of the tragedy. Additionally, the political and economic interests of various parties involved have influenced the shaping of official figures to varying degrees.

The long latency period of radiation-related illnesses adds another layer of complexity to assessing the true number of casualties. Many of the health effects, such as cancer and other radiation-induced diseases, can take years or even decades to manifest. As a result, it becomes challenging to attribute these illnesses directly to the Chernobyl disaster, leading to potential underestimations of the actual impact³⁰.

³⁰ Kuchinskaya, Olga, *op.cit.*

Environmental impacts, too, have been subject to disagreements and uncertainties. While the immediate effects of the disaster, such as the release of radioactive materials into the atmosphere and the contamination of nearby areas, are relatively well-documented, the long-term consequences are still the subject of ongoing research. Genetic mutations in flora and fauna, changes in ecosystems, and the persistence of radioactive contamination in the environment are areas that require further investigation.

The role of scientific studies and independent research cannot be understated in understanding the full extent of the Chernobyl disaster. However, even within the scientific community, there are varying interpretations and conflicting findings. The complex nature of nuclear disasters, combined with the limitations of research methodologies, makes it challenging to reach a consensus on the exact figures and long-term consequences.

To sum up, the disagreements on the official figures concerning the Chernobyl disaster highlight the complexity and challenges involved in assessing the impacts on the population and the environment. The combination of limited data, political and economic interests, the long latency period of health effects, and ongoing scientific research contribute to the discrepancies. While the quest for accurate figures continues, it is essential to recognize the broader significance of the disaster and its lasting effects on human lives and the natural world.

4. The state of diplomacy before and after the disaster: a real accountability of states?

This part therefore leads us to consider the second question that we posed in the introductory part: In the diplomatic world, did this event raise the awareness of the international community about the risks of these installations?

This problematic leads us to develop our reasoning on the effects that Chernobyl may have had on decision-making and international negotiations. This allows us to explore the questions that underlie our problematic: Did the international community become fully aware of the situation and its consequences? Did the diplomatic world rise to the occasion of the disaster through the negotiations and measures taken following the event?

Our analysis will attempt to answer these questions. We will analyse the negotiations and measures taken by the international community in the aftermath of the accident, and then in the long term. In addition, we will be able to discuss the accountability of the international community in the face of this type of accident.

4.1. Before 1986: the state of international nuclear diplomacy

Although 1986 marked a breakthrough on awareness of nuclear issues, this does not mean that no international standards and regulations existed before this event. This section therefore aims to shed light on the state of the law and regulations before the Chernobyl nuclear disaster.

Discussions at the international level concerning nuclear energy for civilian purposes began after the Second World War, in the context of the Cold War. These debates began in particular with the creation of the International Atomic Energy Commission by the United Nations General Assembly³¹. The 1955 Geneva Conference also marked the beginning of discussions on the regulation of nuclear energy and its development for peaceful purposes³². Held from 18 to 23 July, this conference aimed to reach agreements on international peace and security. Within this framework, discussions concerning the civil use of nuclear energy and related safety issues took place but did not lead to any agreements.

From this key moment, international organisations were created throughout the second half of the 20th century, creating bases for negotiations and discussions on nuclear issues at the inter-state level. This is the case of the IAEA³³, created in 1957 after the failure of the 1946 commission, which "*organises its activities around two main axes: one concerns the control of nuclear materials and non-proliferation, the other concerns all activities related to the peaceful uses of nuclear energy*"³⁴. In these years, Europe also developed Euratom³⁵, which deals at European level with cooperation in the field of civil nuclear energy in order to create "*the conditions for the development of a powerful nuclear industry in the Community*"³⁶. Subsequently, in 1960, a Convention on Third Party Liability in the Field of Nuclear Energy³⁷ was adopted, which focused especially on compensation for damage caused to the affected population in the event of nuclear accidents³⁸. Finally, the Vienna Convention on Civil Liability for Nuclear Damage of 1963 was devoted to the same subject matter as the Paris Convention. However, at that time, while the Paris Convention was only applicable between a group of OEEC³⁹ states, the other was intended to be applicable worldwide⁴⁰.

All this has led to the development of some international regulation of civil nuclear power. However, a lot of regulation falls back to the national level, which results in a lack of international coordination and therefore potential difficulties in case of a nuclear accident.

³¹ Aron, Alexandre. Le contrôle international de l'énergie atomique. *Politique étrangère*, 1946, vol. 11, no 5, p. 465-488.

³² Terrisse, Jean, L'énergie nucléaire au service de l'homme. *Esprit (1940-)*, 1956, p. 167-180.

³³ International Atomic Energy Agency

³⁴ Autorité de sûreté nucléaire, *L'Agence internationale de l'énergie atomique (AIEA)*, [Online]. [Accessed 13 May 2023]. Available from: <https://www.asn.fr/tout-sur-l-asn/relations-internationales/l-agence-internationale-de-l-energie-atomique-aiea>

³⁵ European Atomic Energy Community

³⁶ Strohl, Pierre. Tchernobyl et le problème des obligations internationales relatives aux accidents nucléaires. *Politique étrangère*, 1986, p. 1035-1054.

³⁷ Also called Paris convention of 1960

³⁸ In the preamble the purpose is clearly expressed and worded as follows: "*desiring to provide adequate and equitable compensation to persons who suffer damage caused by nuclear accidents, while taking the necessary steps to avoid hampering the development of the production and uses of nuclear energy for peaceful purposes*". OCDE, Convention sur la responsabilité civile dans le domaine de l'énergie nucléaire (Convention de Paris), [Online]. [Accessed 13 May 2023]. Available from <https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/public/doc/199/199.fr.pdf>

³⁹ Organisation for European economic Co-operation

⁴⁰ Lamm, Vanda, Le Protocole d'amendement de la Convention de Vienne de 1963, *Bulletin de droit nucléaire*, 2006, vol. 61.

Moreover, these conventions, although ratified by some countries, do not apply to all, so in the event of an accident, states may have different prerogatives, which weakens the system.

4.2. Accountability and awareness of the international community? The post-1986 period

The Chernobyl disaster, which occurred on April 26, 1986, not only had profound effects on the environment and public health but also sparked significant diplomatic repercussions. In fact, in order to deal with the consequences of the nuclear disaster that occurred, many debates and negotiations took place after Chernobyl and contributed to the evolution of international law. However, have these developments progressed sufficiently? Do states sufficiently ensure the safety of these facilities? Are they held responsible in case of a disaster? Many authors have asked these questions and tried to find answers.

This exploration will analyze the extent to which the Chernobyl event raised awareness among the international diplomatic community about the risks associated with nuclear facilities. By examining the diplomatic responses, collaborations, and policy changes that followed the disaster, this study sheds light on the lasting impact of Chernobyl on global nuclear safety discourse.

We will first discuss the immediate measures taken to limit the damage, then the negotiations that took place and the standards and regulations that emerged or did not emerge. Throughout this discussion we will analyse the effectiveness of these mechanisms and discuss whether states are sufficiently aware of these challenges.

a. Immediate measures after the nuclear accident.

Firstly, being a disaster that had repercussions not only on the territory where it occurred but also on the territory of other states, the USSR should have immediately informed its neighbours about the disaster. However, the USSR did not do so, and it was only on 14 May that the country's leader, Mr Gorbachev, spoke publicly about the incident. This was partly prompted by pressure from other countries that had discovered the problem earlier. Indeed, on 28 April, two days after the reactor explosion, workers at a nuclear power plant in Sweden reported heavy radiation from Chernobyl⁴¹. And the next day, the US obtained images of the site from a spy satellite⁴².

Various measures were taken as soon as the disaster struck, and the international community became aware of it in the days that followed. First regional, then national and finally international, measures were taken, and aid put in place. Indeed, as soon as the incident occurred, many firefighters, although not equipped for this type of disaster, arrived. During the

⁴¹ Forsmark: how Sweden alerted the world about the danger of Chernobyl disaster, *News: European Parliament*, [Online]. 15 May 2014. [Accessed 13 May 2023]. Available from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20140514STO47018/forsmark-how-sweden-alerted-the-world-about-the-danger-of-chernobyl-disaster>

⁴² Chernobyl: Timeline of Events, [Online]. [Accessed 13 May 2023]. Available from: <https://www.atomicarchive.com/science/power/chernobyl-timeline.html>

night local officials met to try to take immediate action. What emerged was the blocking of roads and transport routes around Pripyat, the town where the Chernobyl workers lived, and the shutting down of reactors 1, 2 and 3, although the latter were reopened months later⁴³. Many attempts were made to prevent too much radioactivity being released. This is the case of the numerous helicopters used to throw sand, clay and other materials to cover the reactor core. Other actions such as evacuation of people⁴⁴, cleaning of the surroundings⁴⁵, closing of schools in a certain area, but also government recommendations were taken only 36 hours after the disaster or even up to a week later⁴⁶.

The Chernobyl disaster also highlighted the need for assistance and humanitarian efforts. Countries and organizations provided aid to affected regions, leading to increased diplomatic engagement and collaboration. International actors focused on mitigating the immediate consequences of the disaster, including evacuating and treating affected individuals, monitoring radiation levels, and supporting environmental remediation efforts.

The USSR was slow to provide information about what had happened and also gave incomplete information. Many countries criticised this lack of communication from the Soviets, but not all countries reacted in the same way. The United States was rather reserved in its criticism and offered technical and humanitarian assistance. In contrast, Western European governments were less cautious in their criticism but still provided medical and technical assistance to the Soviets⁴⁷. It is important to note that in 1986 the law concerning transboundary environmental damage was only slightly developed. Some principles were known to the international community through case law and soft law declarations, such as the declaration of the Stockholm conference. However, there were no international standards obliging states to act in a certain way in case of environmental damage to other countries⁴⁸. Furthermore, as mentioned above, there were few regulations for states on how to behave in the event of a nuclear disaster. This also shows the weakness of the international regime.

These countries were also affected by the radioactivity from the explosion and therefore had to put in place national measures. Although the extent of the damage was difficult to calculate due to the lack of information, many countries developed Protective Action Guides to help health authorities protect public health⁴⁹. Measures in agriculture, health and the environment in general have been established in countries around the world. However, these have been initiated at different times and completed at different times, whether at local, regional or national level⁵⁰. At the international level there is also a lack of uniformity in international standards. This makes it difficult to assess the effectiveness and usefulness of these actions.

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ 115,000 people were evacuated from Pripyat and surrounding villages.

⁴⁵ The Soviet Union not only drained the water below the reactor, but also bulldozed or treated many of the surrounding villages and forests, and killed contaminated animals.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Fabrikant, Jacob I., The Chernobyl Disaster: An International Perspective. *Industrial Crisis Quarterly*, 1987, vol. 1, no. 4, p. 2–12.

⁴⁸ McClatchey, Deveraux F, Chernobyl and Sandoz One Decade Later: The Evolution of State Responsibility for International Disasters, 1986-1996. *Ga. J. Int'l & Comp. L.*, 1995, vol. 25, p. 659-680.

⁴⁹ Fabrikant, Jacob, *op.cit.*

⁵⁰ Fabrikant, Jacob, *op.cit.*

Thus, many actions were implemented to deal with the disaster, but this was done in a partly haphazard way and showed the shortcomings of the protective measures in case of such an event. With Chernobyl we also saw a weakness in the international mechanisms that were almost non-existent. According to McClatchey, diplomatic measures would have a better capacity to influence the conduct of states⁵¹. However, the international community did try to put in place measures to protect people and the environment, but this was a relative failure as actions were not uniform.

In the longer term, this event may also have led to initiatives at the international level regarding the regulations that can be applied to this type of case. Thus, a turning point in world diplomacy took place and resulted in negotiations that were able to include nuclear power in their agenda. However, has this been sufficient? Were states able to develop adequate measures and rules for such situations? This is what will be discussed in the next few lines.

b. Long-term development of international diplomacy

The Chernobyl disaster occurred during the late Cold War era, a period marked by heightened geopolitical tensions and the arms race between the Soviet Union and the United States. The event shattered the perception of the Soviet Union's nuclear prowess and raised concerns among the international community about the safety and security of nuclear facilities worldwide. Diplomatic channels played a crucial role in responding to the disaster, fostering international cooperation, and shaping global nuclear safety agendas.

In the aftermath of Chernobyl, various diplomatic efforts aimed to address the risks posed by nuclear facilities. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) assumed a central role in coordinating international responses and providing technical expertise. The IAEA facilitated information sharing, offered guidance on safety measures, and conducted assessments of nuclear facilities worldwide. In fact, after the disaster, the IAEA cooperate with states and other organs of the United- Nations to create the Chernobyl Forum. *“The Forum’s mission was to reach consensus on the environmental consequences and health effects attributable to radiation exposure arising from the accident, as well as to provide advice on environmental remediation, special health care programs, and areas where further research is required.”*⁵². More generally, the Agency has made it possible to conduct numerous analyses and studies on the subject and has tried to strengthen international collaboration in the field⁵³.

Additionally, bilateral and multilateral collaborations emerged, fostering exchanges of expertise, technology, and best practices in nuclear safety. The Chernobyl disaster prompted significant policy changes and the establishment of new safety protocols in the diplomatic arena. The incident emphasized the necessity of robust international standards for nuclear

⁵¹ McClatchey, Deveraux, *op.cit.*

⁵² Hinton, Thomas G, *et alli*, Radiation-induced effects on plants and animals: Findings of the United-Nations Chernobyl Forum. *Health, Physics*. November 2007. Vol. 93, no. 5, p. 427.

⁵³ Hidayatullah, H, *et alli*, Design and technology development for small modular reactors–Safety expectations, prospects and impediments of their deployment. *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, 2015, vol. 79, p. 127-135.

safety. Diplomatic negotiations resulted in the development of conventions and agreements addressing nuclear safety, emergency preparedness, and liability issues.

The best example of this collaboration and implementation of binding measures are the various conventions on nuclear safety adopted under the auspices of the IAEA⁵⁴. One of the best known is the 1994 Convention on Nuclear Safety. It imposes several rights and obligations on states that must be respected. It also implies the notion of responsibility for nuclear safety for the country hosting such facilities and refers in particular to the Convention on the Physical Protection of Nuclear Material of 1979, the Convention on Early Notification of a Nuclear Accident of 1986, and the Convention on Assistance in the Case of a Nuclear Accident or Radiological Emergency⁵⁵. The Convention on Early Notification of a Nuclear Accident and the Convention on Assistance in the Case of a Nuclear Accident or Radiological Emergency, both sponsored by the IAEA, aimed to enhance information sharing and cooperation among nations in response to nuclear accidents. These agreements helped establish clear channels for reporting incidents, facilitating prompt international assistance, and ensuring transparency. Thus, all these conventions set out principles that apply to the contracting parties and show the awareness of the international community on the subject, which is ready to make certain commitments on the international level.

The diplomatic world also put strong pressure for the definitive closure of reactors 1, 2 and 3 which had been reopened after the disaster. Indeed, the G7 members⁵⁶, the European Commission and Ukraine combined their efforts to do so⁵⁷. They concluded an agreement in 1995 to close Chernobyl by 2000 at the latest. These countries have therefore supported initiatives such as “*short-term safety upgrades at Chernobyl Unit 3, decommissioning the entire Chernobyl site, developing ways to address shutdown impacts on workers and their families, and identifying investments needed to meet Ukraine’s future electrical power needs.*”⁵⁸.

Moreover, the Chernobyl disaster spurred revisions and improvements in domestic nuclear safety regulations in many countries. Diplomatic efforts were directed toward sharing lessons learned from the disaster and promoting the adoption of more stringent safety measures. This involved diplomatic negotiations, technical collaborations, and capacity-building initiatives to strengthen national regulatory frameworks.

c. Accountability and awareness of states?

From what we have discussed above, we can see that international and national activity in the development of nuclear-related measures and cooperation is booming. However, there are blockages to these developments that call into question the accountability of the international community.

⁵⁴ Les conventions sur la sûreté nucléaire, [Online]. 6 April 2018. [Accessed 16 May 2023]. Available from: <https://www.iaea.org/fr/themes/les-conventions-sur-la-surete-nucleaire>

⁵⁵ Convention on nuclear safety, IAEA, INFCIRC/449, 1994, preamble

⁵⁶ The G7 is composed by France, USA, Canada, Japan, Italy, United Kingdom and Germany

⁵⁷ Backgrounder on Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant Accident, *NRC Web*, [Online]. [Accessed 17 May 2023]. Available from: <https://www.nrc.gov/reading-rm/doc-collections/fact-sheets/chernobyl-bg.html>

⁵⁸ Ibid.

While the Chernobyl disaster raised awareness of the risks associated with nuclear facilities, it also generated debates and challenges in the diplomatic realm. Disagreements emerged regarding the sharing of information, the balance between transparency and national security concerns, and the responsibilities of international organizations versus individual states in ensuring nuclear safety.

Furthermore, the differing priorities and perspectives of states with nuclear capabilities shaped diplomatic discourse. Some countries emphasized the need to prioritize safety measures and adopt stricter regulations, while others raised concerns about the economic implications and potential restrictions on nuclear energy development. The book *Business Power and Conflict in International Environmental Politics*, aims to show how economic and business considerations shape the outcomes in the Environmental Diplomacy⁵⁹. According to the author, the nuclear industry is a way to benefit from environmental restrictions of other energy fields. However, with the Chernobyl accident and the development of national and international regulations, we may witness some changes in behaviour.

The development of new environmental and safety regulations has been an undeniable proof of empowerment. However, it is still up to the state to choose whether or not to bind itself to these conventions. The principle of sovereignty is only partially limited by certain general principles of law, but this can easily be circumvented as there are few or no legal mechanisms to condemn a state. It is therefore necessary to rely on diplomatic pressure and civil society to bring the most reluctant states into line with existing international obligations.

5. Conclusion

Our analysis was therefore able to consider the various facets of Chernobyl. We were able to study in depth the debates surrounding this event, which is still a historical landmark, deeply rooted in society. Thus, studying the Chernobyl disaster serves as a crucial lesson for the nuclear industry and policymakers worldwide. It highlights the need for robust safety protocols, thorough training of personnel, effective communication and coordination, and transparency in sharing information. By learning from the mistakes of the past, we can work towards preventing similar disasters and ensuring the safety of nuclear facilities for the benefit of humanity and the environment. However, this will require a great deal of international cooperation and coordination, which is a major challenge for this field but can be helped by the civil society pressure.

⁵⁹ Falkner, Robert, *Business Power and Conflict in International Environmental Politics*, Palgrave Macmillan, 2008.

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